

Assessment of the effect of air humidity and temperature on convective drying of apple with pulsed electric field pretreatment

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

PEF
Electroporation
Non-dehumidified air
Dehumidified air
Quality

ABSTRACT

This research aims at assessing the impact of pulsed electric field (PEF) pretreatment and various properties of drying agent (absolute humidity, temperature) on the course of convective drying (CD) of apples. Moreover, the selected quality indicators of obtained dried materials (dry matter content, water activity, hygroscopicity, rehydration, color, total phenolic content, antioxidant activity) have been evaluated. As a result of increased permeabilization of cells, PEF reduced time of CD of apples even by 20%. However, lower total phenolic content and antioxidant activity in PEF-pretreated dried samples were observed. With the use of PEF, the release of phenolic compounds from the cellular structures of the apple tissue could occur, making them more susceptible to thermal degradation. After introducing the dehumidification system, an increase in the drying time of apples was observed. It could be so due to case hardening, which further deteriorated the reconstitution properties of the obtained dried materials.

1. Introduction

The ever-developing food industry is constantly aiming at introducing innovative technologies to reduce production costs, improve product quality, and create new products to be introduced to the market. Modern consumers are conscious individuals, paying special attention to food with high nutritional value, that is produced using environmentally friendly methods. This trend favors the implementation of pulsed electric field (PEF) technology for its use on an industrial scale (Nowosad, Sujka, Pankiewicz, & Kowalski, 2021).

Non-thermal food processing with PEF involves the use of short electric pulses with high electric field strength, which causes the phenomenon of electroporation (Plazzotta, Ibarz, Manzocco, & Martín-Belloso, 2021). As a result, the permeability of the cell membrane increases, which, depending on its type - either reversible or irreversible, may cause biochemical and physiological modifications of the cell or even lead to its death. Compared to traditional pretreatments, PEF stands out among others thanks to shorter processing time, lower treatment temperature, lower energy consumption, no environmental pollution or chemical residue (Zhang, Zhang, Yang, & Zhao, 2022).

Fresh vegetables and fruits contain 80–90% of water, which is stored

in various cellular structures. Such a high water content is the main reason for the perishability of these types of agricultural products, so their proper preservation is important (Mahiuddin, Khan, Kumar, Rahman, & Karim, 2018). One of the ways of preserving fruit and vegetables is drying, during which water is evaporated to a sufficiently low level, which prevents, among other elements, the growth of microorganisms responsible for food spoilage (Dai et al., 2015). The course of the drying process and the quality of the obtained dried material are affected by numerous factors, such as the properties of the fresh material, the type of drying or the principal drying parameters (Dai et al., 2015; Darıcı and Şen, 2015; Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Amenorfe, et al., 2018). That is why it is crucial to properly select the method and process parameters for the type of material meant for drying.

So far, the influence of different air humidity and temperature on convective drying of apple (Kaya, Aydın, & Demirtaş, 2007), apricot (Dai et al., 2015), banana (Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Amenorfe, et al., 2018; Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Oteng-Darko, et al., 2018), kiwifruit (Darıcı and Şen, 2015; Kaya, Aydın, & Kolaylı, 2010), quince (Kaya, Aydın, Demirtaş, & Akgün, 2007), carrot (Sarpong et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2020), yam (Ju et al., 2016), and shiitake mushroom (Subramaniam, Wen, Zhang, & Jing, 2021) has been studied. Unfortunately, none of the

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2023.115455>

Received 5 April 2023; Received in revised form 20 October 2023; Accepted 22 October 2023

Available online 23 October 2023

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above-mentioned studies addressed the effect of PEF pretreatment on drying with dehumidified air.

Therefore, the aim of this research was to assess the effect of pulsed electric field pretreatment and different drying conditions (air humidity and temperature) on the course of convective drying of apples and quality of the obtained dried materials (dry matter content, water activity, hygroscopicity, rehydration, color, total phenolic content, antioxidant activity).

The study was conducted using laboratory scale dryer and PEF device that can work as laboratory, pilot, and small industrial system. Nevertheless, obtained results could serve as a guideline for scaling up the process into industrial conditions as they show how parameters of drying and pulsed electric field pretreatment influence both drying kinetics, water activity, hygroscopicity, rehydration, color, total phenolic content, as well as antioxidant activity. However, as it is worth highlighting that future works in this field should focus also on the effect of PEF on the texture of material dried by convective method (both in dried and rehydrated form), as it was not studied in the current research. Moreover, future works in that area should focus on the assessment of scaled up process.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

The examination was performed on apples (variant "Golden delicious"), which were derived from the Experimental Fields of the Department of Fruit Growing of the Warsaw University of Life Sciences (Warsaw, Poland). After spending not more than a week in the cold storage (approx. 5 °C), the most homogeneous specimens in terms of external appearance were picked for the research. Directly before the start of the examination, apples were rinsed with tap water and left for attaining room temperature (approx. 20 °C). Fresh apples contained approx. 5.897 g of water per 1 g of dry matter.

Obtained dried apples were packed into laminate pouches (PET/Al/PE) impervious to gas, light, and vapor. All the analyses were conducted after one week of storage (time necessary for the stabilization of dried materials).

2.2. Pulsed electric field pretreatment

Pretreatment of the apples consisting of an application of the pulsed electric field (PEF) was carried out in a batch unit (PEFPilot™ Dual System, Elea Vertriebs- und Vermarktungsgesellschaft mbH, Quakenbrück, Germany). For that purpose, chamber with a capacity of 2 L was used, which contained two parallel electrodes made of stainless steel, separated from each other by 240 mm. After placing a single apple inside, the chamber was then filled with tap water (at temperature of approx. 21 °C, and conductivity of 718 µS/cm) to a level, which ensured total immersion of the treated material into conductive medium. Total input of the treatment chamber (apple plus water) equaled approx. 1.5 kg. Remaining process parameters were set as follows: 20 Hz of pulse frequency, 7 µs of pulse duration, 24 kV of electrode voltage, 1 kV/cm of electric field strength, and specific energy input in amount of 1, 3.5, and 6 kJ/kg (PEF energy input). The amount of rectangular pulses depended on the specific energy input (W_s , kJ/kg), which, as well as electric field strength (E , kV/cm), was calculated according to the following equations:

$$W_s = \frac{IUt}{m} \quad (1)$$

$$E = \frac{U}{d} \quad (2)$$

where: d - the distance between two parallel electrodes [cm]; I - the current [A]; m - the total input of the treatment chamber [kg]; n - the

amount of rectangular pulses [-]; t - the duration of the pulse [s]; U - the electrode voltage [kV].

The effectiveness of the PEF on the treated apple tissue was assessed using measurement of electrical conductivity (pH/conductivity meter CPC-401, Elmtron, Zabrze, Poland). Based on obtained results, the CDI (cell disintegration index) was calculated according to the literature (Lebovka, Shynkaryk, & Vorobiev, 2007):

$$CDI = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_i}{\sigma_d - \sigma_i} \quad (3)$$

where: σ - the electrical conductivity of PEF-treated apple tissue [µS]; σ_d - the electrical conductivity of total damaged apple tissue (PEF energy input of 63 kJ/kg) [µS]; σ_i - the electrical conductivity of intact apple tissue [µS].

2.3. Convective drying

Untreated and PEF-treated apples were manually cut into 5 mm thick slices with diameter of approx. 70 mm. After that, the cores were removed and the prepared slices were cut into four equal quarters.

Obtained quarters of apple slices were dried in a laboratory convective dryer, which was presented schematically in Fig. 1. Depending on the process conditions, there was only part C used (convective dryer), or all parts A-C (convective dryer with dehumidification system). Aiming to obtain dehumidified air, there was a need to implement additional devices such as: cooling unit (MTA, TAEvo TECH020, MTA, Tribano, Italy) - A, dehumidifier (ML270, Munters, Sweden) consisted of condensation part - B (a), and adsorption part - B (b). Process parameters were set as follows: air absolute humidity (1.5, 10 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), air velocity (1.5 m/s), tray load (1.24 kg/m²). Drying air flowed parallel to the dried material, which was arranged in one layer on the perforated tray.

The weight of the apples placed on the drying tray was continuously monitored and documented in 5 min intervals, without any disruption of the process. The end of the drying process was considered to be a state when the weight of the drying material did not change for 15 min. Every variant of drying was repeated three times. This method allowed to determine the final drying time - time necessary to obtain moisture ratio (MR) of 0.02 (reference point). MR was calculated according to the literature (Wang et al., 2021):

$$MR = \frac{M_t}{M_0} \quad (4)$$

where: M_t - moisture content in apple during drying [g H₂O/g d.m.]; M_0 - initial moisture content in apple [5.897 g H₂O/g d.m.].

2.4. Dry matter content

Determination of the dry matter content (d.m.c.) was performed in compliance with the AOAC 920.15, 2002 standard (Mannozi et al., 2017), three times for each sample.

2.5. Water activity

The measurement of the water activity (a_w) was accomplished with the utilization of a hygrometer (AquaLab CX-2, Decagon Devices, Pullman, WA, USA) at room temperature (approx. 20 °C), threefold. The device was calibrated at temperature of 25 °C using steam distilled water ($a_w = 1.000 \pm 0.003$) and verification standards (METER Group, Pullman, WA, USA): 0.50 mol/kg KCl ($a_w = 0.984 \pm 0.003$), 2.33 mol/kg NaCl ($a_w = 0.920 \pm 0.003$), 6.00 mol/kg NaCl ($a_w = 0.760 \pm 0.003$), 8.57 mol/kg LiCl ($a_w = 0.500 \pm 0.003$), and 13.41 mol/kg LiCl ($a_w = 0.250 \pm 0.003$).

Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of the drying setup used in this research; A - cooling unit, B - dehumidifier (a - condensation part, b - adsorption part), C - convective dryer (c - air flow regulator valve, d - air heater, e - product, f - drying tray, g - computer, h - balance) (Matys, Wiktor, Dadan, & Witrowa-Rajchert, 2021).

Fig. 2. Cell disintegration index (CDI) of PEF-treated (1 kV/cm) apples depending on the various PEF energy inputs; the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

2.6. Hygroscopic properties

Aiming to determine the ability of water vapor adsorption, slices of dried apples were left in a desiccator over a saturated solution of NaCl ($a_w = 0.75$) at room temperature (approx. 20 °C) for 72 h. The analysis was repeated three times, and results were expressed as ratio ($H_{72 h}$) stated hereafter:

$$H_{72 h} = \frac{m_t}{m_0} \quad (5)$$

where: m_t - the mass of the slice after analysis [g]; m_0 - the mass of the slice before analysis [g].

2.7. Rehydration properties

In order to evaluate the ability of water absorption, slices of dried apples were immersed in distilled water at temperature approx. 20 °C for 30 min (mass ratio 1:100, respectively). After that, rehydrated samples were softly blotted utilizing filter paper. The analysis was repeated three times for each sample, and results were expressed as rehydration ratio (RR) stated below:

$$RR = \frac{m_t}{m_0} \quad (6)$$

where: m_t - the mass of the slice after rehydration [g]; m_0 - the mass of

the slice before rehydration [g].

2.8. Color

The measurement of the color was realized with the usage of CR-5 colorimeter (Konica-Minolta, Tokyo, Japan). Analysis was performed in the reflection, and color parameters were defined in the $L^*a^*b^*$ color space (CIELAB). The remaining measurement parameters were set as follows: 3 mm of diameter, standard observer CIE 2°, illuminant D65. Each sample was analyzed tenfold. Total color difference (ΔE), browning index (BI) and hue angle (H) were calculated in accordance to the equations:

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(L_d^* - L_f^*)^2 + (a_d^* - a_f^*)^2 + (b_d^* - b_f^*)^2} \quad (7)$$

$$BI = \frac{[100(x - 0.31)]}{0.17} \quad (8)$$

$$x = \frac{(a_d^* + 1.75L_d^*)}{5.645L_d^* + a_d^* - 3.012b_d^*} \quad (9)$$

$$H = \text{ArcTan} \frac{b_d^*}{a_d^*} \quad (10)$$

for values in I quadrant (+a; +b),

$$H = 180 + \text{ArcTan} \frac{b_d^*}{a_d^*} \quad (11)$$

for values in II quadrant (-a; +b),

where: L_d^* , a_d^* , b_d^* - values of L^* , a^* , b^* color parameters obtained for dried apples [-]; L_f^* , a_f^* , b_f^* - values of L^* , a^* , b^* color parameters obtained for fresh apple [-].

2.9. Preparation of the extracts

Aiming to quantify chemical compounds that the obtained dried apples contained, the ethanolic extracts needed to be prepared. For that purpose, 1 g of material previously ground with the use of an analytical mill (A11 basic, IKA®-Werke GmbH & Co. KG, Staufen, Germany) was mixed with 20 mL of ethanol-water solution, 80:20 mL/mL. The obtained solution was gently heated for 3 min (not boiled), then filtered, and filled up to the total volume of 50 mL. Ethanolic extracts, which were prepared in duplicate for each of the sample, were used in chemical analyses (determination of the total phenolic content and the

antioxidant activity).

2.10. Total phenolic content

The Folin-Ciocalteu's method was utilized to determine the total phenolic content (TPC) in dried apples (Singleton, Orthofer, & Lamuela-Raventós, 1999). Distilled water, ethanolic extract of dried apple, and Folin-Ciocalteu reagent were dispensed one by one to the glass tube in the volume of 4.92, 0.18, and 0.3 mL, respectively. Three minutes after mixing, supersaturated sodium carbonate solution (in volume of 0.6 mL) was added, and the total content of a glass tube was mixed once again. The prepared solution was kept in a dark place at room temperature (approx. 20 °C) for 60 min. Absorbance of that solution was measured in regard to a blank sample (ethanolic extract of the dried apple was replaced with ethanol-water solution, 80:20 mL/mL) via spectrophotometer (Helios Thermo Electron version 7.03, Thermo Electron Corporation, Waltham, MA, USA). The wavelength equaled 750 nm. Each ethanolic extract was analyzed twice, meaning that each obtained dried apple was analyzed four times. In that determination gallic acid was used as a standard, so the obtained results were expressed as milligrams of gallic acid (GAE) per 100 g of dry matter (d.m.).

2.11. Antioxidant activity

2.11.1. DPPH assay

The antioxidant activity of dried apples was evaluated on the basis of the scavenging degree of DPPH• radicals by antioxidants contained in the prepared ethanolic extracts (Brand-Williams, Cuvelier, & Berset, 1995). Firstly, the free radical solution of DPPH• and the solution for the measurement were prepared according to the literature (Rybak, Wiktor, Witrowa-Rajchert, Parniakov, & Nowacka, 2021). Ethanolic extract of the dried apple (in volume of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4 mL) and ethanol-water solution, 80:20 mL/mL (in volume of 1.9, 1.8, 1.7, and 1.6 mL) were dispensed to the glass tube (total volume equaled 2 mL). After that, 2 mL of the free radical solution of DPPH• were added to each glass tube. The total content of the glass tube was mixed. The prepared solution was kept in a dark place at room temperature (approx. 20 °C) for 30 min. Absorbance of that solution was measured with the use of a spectrophotometer (Helios Thermo Electron version 7.03, Thermo Electron Corporation, Waltham, MA, USA). The wavelength equaled 515 nm. Each ethanolic extract was analyzed twice, so each obtained dried apple was analyzed four times. The obtained results were expressed as EC₅₀ coefficient, which stands for an extract concentration necessary for a 50% reduction of the initial amount of DPPH• radicals - in milligrams of dry matter (d.m.) per 1 mL of ethanolic extract.

2.11.2. ABTS assay

In addition, the scavenging degree of the ABTS•⁺ radical cations was also evaluated for comparative purposes. Firstly, the free radical solution of ABTS•⁺ and the solution for the measurement were prepared according to the literature (Rybak et al., 2021). Ethanolic extract of the dried apple (in volume of 0.025, 0.050, 0.075, and 0.100 mL) and free radical solution of ABTS•⁺ (in volume of 3 mL) were dispensed to the glass tube. The total content of the glass tube was mixed. The prepared solution was kept in a dark place at room temperature (approx. 20 °C) for 6 min. Absorbance of that solution was measured with the use of a spectrophotometer (Helios Thermo Electron version 7.03, Thermo Electron Corporation, Waltham, MA, USA). The wavelength equaled 734 nm. Each ethanolic extract was analyzed twice, so each obtained dried apple was analyzed four times. The obtained results were expressed as EC₅₀ coefficient, which stands for an extract concentration necessary for a 50% reduction of the initial amount of ABTS•⁺ radical cations - in milligrams of dry matter (d.m.) per 1 mL of ethanolic extract.

2.12. Statistical analysis

Multi-way analysis of variance and Tukey's test (Statistica, version 13, TIBCO Software Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA) were used to examine the significance of the differences between results obtained for the interaction of three categorical factors (air humidity, air temperature, and PEF energy input). The results of this analysis were presented in Figs. 3–12 (a, b) as lowercase letters representing homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$). Moreover, the values of the Partial Eta Squared (η_p^2) were put in Table 1. The values of this indicator can be in the range of 0–1, and the higher value of η_p^2 , the higher impact of given categorical factor on specific dependent variable. Additionally, one-way analysis of variance and Tukey's test were carried out to assess the impact of three categorical factors separately on the several dependent variables (drying time, a_w , H_{72 h}, RR, ΔE , BI, H, TPC, EC₅₀ DPPH, and EC₅₀ ABTS). The results of this analysis were submitted as supplementary material (Tables S1–S10) and described in detail in the chapter "Results and discussion". Moreover, one-way analysis of variance and Tukey's test were used to evaluate the impact of PEF energy input on the CDI, which was presented in Fig. 2 as lowercase letters representing homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effectiveness of the pulsed electric field

The effectiveness of the pulsed electric field on the treated tissue can be assessed using several methods, such as: time-domain nuclear magnetic resonance (TD-NMR), microscopic analysis, or measurement of electrical conductivity (Dellarosa et al., 2016). Using the last one of the above-mentioned methods, it is possible to calculate the CDI (cell disintegration index). This index takes values from 0 (intact tissue) to 1 (totally ruptured tissue) (Lebovka et al., 2007). Based on Fig. 2, the higher the PEF energy input, the higher values of CDI. The achieved tendency is consistent with the literature data (Fauster, Giancaterino, Pittia, & Jaeger, 2020; Matys, Dadan, Witrowa-Rajchert, Parniakov, & Wiktor, 2022; Matys, Witrowa-Rajchert, Parniakov, & Wiktor, 2022; Ostermeier, Giersemehl, Siemer, Töpfl, & Jäger, 2018). Depending on the amount of energy supplied during PEF pretreatment (1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg), the disintegration of apple tissue cells was in the range of 0.07–0.44. The values of CDI depend both on the factors related to the treated material (composition, structure) and on the process parameters used (Alam, Lyng, Frontuto, Marra, & Cinquanta, 2018; Bassey, Cheng, & Sun, 2021; Chauhan, Sayanfar, & Toepfl, 2018; Llavata, García-Pérez, Simal, & Cárcel, 2020).

3.2. Drying kinetics and drying times

Fig. 3a and b show the drying curves and drying times for apples. As expected, the decline in the moisture ratio (MR) slowed down over time. During the initial stage of drying, the unbound water at the surface of the material is removed, followed by the water in micro-capillaries, which explains the decreasing efficiency of the drying process (Kudra, 2004). The multi-way analysis of variance showed that the drying air temperature had the highest impact on the drying time of apples ($\eta_p^2 = 0.993$), followed by PEF energy input ($\eta_p^2 = 0.791$) and air humidity ($\eta_p^2 = 0.673$) (Table 1). According to the one-way analysis of variance, the higher the drying air temperature, the shorter the drying time (Table S1b). This is due to the increase in heat and mass transfer rates at elevated temperature (Darıcı and Şen, 2015). The application of pulsed electric field (PEF) as a pretreatment led to a significant reduction in drying time of apples (up to 20%). PEF, causing permeabilization of cells, probably increased the rate of mass and heat transfer during drying, leading to an increase in the efficiency of this process (Bassey et al., 2021). One-way analysis of variance showed no significant differences between PEF energy input of 1 and 3.5 kJ/kg (Table S1c). Therefore, taking into

Fig. 3. Convective drying curves depending on the air humidity (a - CD, 10 g/m³; b - DA-CD, 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); drying times (min): 1–370 ± 0^l, 2–298 ± 3^{hi}, 3–295 ± 0^h, 4–340 ± 0^k, 5–237 ± 3^{ef}, 6–225 ± 0^{de}, 7–213 ± 3^d, 8–222 ± 3^{de}, 9–170 ± 0^{bc}, 10–155 ± 0^{ab}, 11–150 ± 0^a, 12–155 ± 0^{ab}, 13–370 ± 0^l, 14–322 ± 8^{jk}, 15–320 ± 0^j, 16–315 ± 0^{ij}, 17–252 ± 3^{fg}, 18–260 ± 0^g, 19–254 ± 16^g, 20–248 ± 3^{fg}, 21–175 ± 0^c, 22–170 ± 0^{bc}, 23–175 ± 0^c, 24–160 ± 0^{abc}; the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Water activity (a_w) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 5. Hygroscopicity after 72 h (H_{72h}) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 6. Rehydration ratio (RR) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

account environmental and energy factors, it is worth considering lower energy input to reduce duration of the drying process (Matys, Dadan, et al., 2022). Moreover, according to the results of the one-way analysis

of variance, drying with dehumidified air took longer than drying with non-dehumidified air (Table S1a). This may have been due to case hardening that occurs during drying of significantly moist products with

Fig. 7. Total color difference (ΔE) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 8. Browning index (BI) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 9. Hue angle (H) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 10. Total phenolic content (TPC) in dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m³, b - 1.5 g/m³), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

a usage of a low moist drying agent. Occurrence of this phenomenon could lead to difficulties in terms of water evaporation. In addition, at the same temperature of dry bulb, the enthalpy of hot, humid air is higher than the enthalpy of hot, less humid air, which may result in an

enhancement in the heat transfer values in case of drying with humid air (Ju et al., 2016; Mahiuddin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2020). Nevertheless, there are data in the literature showing that food products are dried faster with dehumidified air than with non-dehumidified air. For

Fig. 11. Antioxidant activity (EC_{50} DPPH) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m^3 , b - 1.5 g/m^3), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Fig. 12. Antioxidant activity (EC_{50} ABTS) of dried apples depending on the air humidity (a - 10 g/m^3 , b - 1.5 g/m^3), air temperature (55, 70, 85 °C), and PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg); the same lowercase letters represent homogeneous groups ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 1

Values of the partial Eta Squared (η_p^2).

Categorical factor	Dependent variable									
	Drying time [min]	a_w [-]	$H_{72 \text{ h}}$ [-]	RR [-]	ΔE [-]	BI [-]	H [°]	TPC [mg GAE/100 g d.m.]	EC_{50} DPPH [mg d. m./mL]	EC_{50} ABTS [mg d. m./mL]
Air humidity [g/m^3]	0.673	0.398	0.688	0.195	0.273	0.050	0.026	0.601	0.933	0.899
Air temperature [°C]	0.993	0.952	0.951	0.061	0.288	0.006	0.001	0.808	0.914	0.876
PEF energy input [kJ/kg]	0.791	0.456	0.296	0.345	0.070	0.277	0.939	0.918	0.927	0.922

example, in a study conducted on shiitake mushrooms (Subramaniam et al., 2021), it was proven that increasing the relative humidity (RH) of the drying air from 0 to 30, 35, 40, 45, and 50% extended the drying process by 33–90%. In addition, it was observed that higher RH reduces the drying rate but has a positive effect on such properties of the dried material as rehydration, shrinkage, and texture. Similarly, in the case of bananas - increasing the RH from 10 to 20 and 30% resulted in an increase in drying time by 3 and 12% (Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Oteng-Darko, et al., 2018) and 4 and 29% (Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Amenorfe, et al., 2018), respectively. Carrots were dried under the same conditions (Sarpong et al., 2019). The obtained results are the same as those of the banana study - an increase in RH from 10 to 20 and 30% led to an increase in drying time by 10 and 30%, respectively. The authors explain the observed trends with a rapid increase in the internal temperature of samples dried with air with a lower RH, which increases the rate of water removal from them. The beneficial effect of dehumidified air on the reduction of drying time was also observed in studies on carrot (Yu et al., 2020), kiwifruit (Darıcı and Şen, 2015; Kaya et al., 2010), quince (Kaya, Aydın, Demirtaş, et al., 2007), and apple (Kaya, Aydın, & Demirtaş, 2007).

3.3. Physicochemical properties

3.3.1. Dry matter content and water activity

The water activity of dried apples in the range of 0.197–0.357 with a dry matter content of 0.036–0.112 g $\text{H}_2\text{O/g}$ d.m. ensured their microbiological and physicochemical stability (Rahman, 2007). The multi-way analysis of variance showed that the drying air temperature had the highest impact on the water activity (a_w) of dried apples ($\eta_p^2 = 0.952$), followed by PEF energy input ($\eta_p^2 = 0.456$) and air humidity ($\eta_p^2 = 0.398$) (Table 1). According to the one-way analysis of variance, the higher the drying air temperature, the lower a_w (Table S2b). This trend is clearly visible in Fig. 4a and b. This trend can be justified by the accelerated evaporation of water occurring at higher temperatures, which affects the moisture content and water activity of the product (Cano-Chauca, Ramos, Stringheta, & Pereira, 2004). Comparing only the effect of PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg) on water activity, significantly lower a_w was observed after supplying the apples with the energy in the amount of 3.5 kJ/kg (Table S2c). One-way analysis of variance showed that with such PEF energy input, drying of apples to a specific MR was the shortest, which indicates the highest evaporation rate. On the other hand, when it comes to air humidity, lower a_w was obtained after drying the apples with dehumidified air (Table S2a). This may have been due to the increased force in evaporation of water with the usage of this type of drying agent (Sarpong et al., 2019).

3.3.2. Hygroscopic properties

Food processing, such as drying or pretreatments, can cause a number of modifications in the physical properties of a given product, both on the macrostructural and microstructural level. These changes may concern, among others, porosity or shrinkage (Joardder, Kumar, & Karim, 2017). The multi-way analysis of variance revealed that the drying air temperature had the highest impact on the hygroscopicity ($H_{72\text{ h}}$) of dried apples ($\eta_p^2 = 0.951$), followed by air humidity ($\eta_p^2 = 0.688$) and PEF energy input ($\eta_p^2 = 0.296$) (Table 1). According to the one-way analysis of variance, the lower the drying temperature, the lower $H_{72\text{ h}}$ (Table S3b). This tendency is clearly visible in Fig. 5a and b. Hygroscopicity is the highest when shrinkage and porosity of the material are the lowest and the highest, respectively (Fijalkowska, Nowacka, & Witrowa-Rajchert, 2017). Drying of apples at air temperature of 55 °C lasted the longest (Fig. 3a and b). At low drying rates, the shrinkage of the material is significant (Dehghannya, Farshad, & Khakbaz Heshmati, 2018; Khraisheh, McMinn, & Magee, 2004; Mahiuddin et al., 2018), which may limit the water vapor adsorption ability of the material. Moreover, taking into account only the effect of drying air humidity, according to the one-way analysis of variance, apples dried with dehumidified air exhibited lower $H_{72\text{ h}}$ than the apples dried with non-dehumidified air (Table S3a). As mentioned above, air with reduced humidity could have caused case hardening of the material (Mahiuddin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2020) and thus created a barrier to water vapor adsorption. Comparing only the effect of PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg) on hygroscopicity, significantly lower $H_{72\text{ h}}$ was observed after supplying the apples with the energy in the amount of 6 kJ/kg (Table S3c). As the degree of material damage increases, its hygroscopic properties tend to be lower (Fijalkowska et al., 2017; Matys, Dadan, et al., 2022). As shown in Fig. 2, the highest PEF energy input resulted in the largest disintegration of apple tissue cells, which may explain the significantly lower $H_{72\text{ h}}$ value obtained in this case.

3.3.3. Rehydration properties

Structural changes caused by food processing can also affect the dried products' ability to reabsorb water (Telfser and Gómez Galindo, 2019). The multi-way analysis of variance showed that only PEF energy input and air humidity had a significant effect on the rehydration ratio (RR) of dried apples (η_p^2 values equaled 0.345 and 0.195, respectively) (Table 1). One-way analysis of variance (Table S4b) showed that the application of pulsed electric field (PEF) as a pretreatment led to a significant reduction in the RR of dried apples (regardless of the amount of energy supplied). This tendency is clearly visible in Fig. 6a and b only for drying air temperature of 55 and 70 °C. The phenomenon of electroporation occurring during PEF leads to damage to the structure of the material by creating pores in it (Llavata et al., 2020). Perhaps apple tissue injury at the CDI level of 0.07–0.44 refrained the initial water content to be replicated. Considering only the effect of drying air humidity on rehydration, it can be stated that apples dried with the usage of dehumidified air exhibited a lower RR than apples dried with non-dehumidified air (Table S4a). This trend has also been observed in the research on mushrooms (Subramaniam et al., 2021). As in the case of hygroscopicity, the observed phenomenon may be justified by the stiffness of the apple's surface, which could be formed during drying by air with reduced humidity (Mahiuddin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2020).

3.3.4. Color

Color is an important quality parameter as it determines the acceptance of food by the consumer (Osae, Essilfie, Alolga, Bonah, et al., 2020). Based on the measured color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) of dried apples, the total color difference (ΔE) was calculated in relation to the fresh apple (L^* : 77.4 ± 0.3 ; a^* : 2.9 ± 0.4 ; b^* : 17.7 ± 1.9). The multi-way analysis of variance showed that the drying air temperature had the highest impact on the ΔE of dried apples ($\eta_p^2 = 0.288$), followed by air humidity ($\eta_p^2 = 0.273$) and PEF energy input ($\eta_p^2 = 0.070$) (Table 1). According to the results of the one-way analysis of variance, drying of

apples at 55 and 85 °C resulted in significantly lower ΔE than drying of this material at 70 °C (Table S5b). This tendency is especially visible in Fig. 7b (Fig. 7a - less variation). The lowest air temperature provided gentle drying conditions (Ostermeier et al., 2018), while the highest air temperature significantly reduced the time required to remove water from apples (Fig. 3a and b). The likely effect was to reduce the rate of enzymatic and non-enzymatic browning of the material, which can occur during the drying process (Jaeger, Janositz, & Knorr, 2010; Wiktor et al., 2016). Taking into account only the effect of drying air humidity, 1.5 and 10 g/m³, lower ΔE was obtained after drying the apples with the air of higher humidity (Table S5a). Similar results were obtained in studies conducted on bananas (Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Amenorfe, et al., 2018; Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Oteng-Darko, et al., 2018) and carrots (Sarpong et al., 2019). The conditions of convective drying are conducive to oxidative reactions, the effects of which are intensified by lower humidity and higher temperature of the drying air (Sarpong et al., 2019; Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Amenorfe, et al., 2018). In addition, as mentioned above, drying of the apples with dehumidified air took longer than drying with non-dehumidified air, which could also negatively affect the color of the material. Comparing only the effect of PEF energy input (0, 1, 3.5, 6 kJ/kg) on the color of dried apples, significantly higher ΔE was observed after supplying the material with the energy in the amount of 3.5 kJ/kg (Table S5c). The phenomenon of electroporation occurring during PEF can both promote enzymatic browning of food (by releasing reaction substrates from cells) and reduce it (by partially inactivating enzymes). The observed effect depends on the parameters used during PEF pretreatment and the properties of the treated material (Osae, Essilfie, Alolga, Akaba, et al., 2020; Tylewicz et al., 2017).

The second color parameter calculated from the measured values of L^* , a^* and b^* is the browning index (BI), which is shown in Fig. 8a and b. When, for example, enzymatic and/or non-enzymatic browning, ascorbic acid browning, formation of browning pigments or decomposition of pigments occur during food processing, then the values of this indicator increase (Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Oteng-Darko, et al., 2018). The multi-way analysis of variance revealed that only PEF energy input and air humidity had a significant effect on the BI of dried apples (η_p^2 values equaled 0.277 and 0.050, respectively) (Table 1). Analyzing the impact of each categorical factor separately (using one-way analysis of variance), the highest BI was achieved for apples treated with PEF (regardless of the amount of applied energy) (Table S6b) and dried with dehumidified air (Table S6a). As mentioned above, lower humidity of drying agent intensifies oxidative reactions which can negatively affect the color, and PEF can promote enzymatic browning of treated material.

The last color parameter calculated is the hue angle (H) and it is presented in Fig. 9a and b. It is an indicator for color classification, which takes values in the range of 0–360° (0 and 360° - red; 90° yellow; 180° green; 270° blue) (McLellan, Lind, & Kime, 1995). The multi-way analysis of variance showed that only PEF energy input and air humidity had a significant effect on the H of dried apples (η_p^2 values equaled 0.939 and 0.026, respectively) (Table 1). Analyzing the impact of each categorical factor separately (using one-way analysis of variance), in accordance with the results obtained for ΔE and BI, the use of pretreatment with a pulsed electric field (Table S7c), and drying of apples with dehumidified air (Table S7a), and a temperature of 70 °C (Table S7b) led to obtain H values near red, while materials untreated with PEF and dried with non-dehumidified air exhibited H values closer to yellow.

3.3.5. Total phenolic content

The multi-way analysis of variance revealed that PEF energy input had the highest impact on total phenolic content (TPC) in dried apples ($\eta_p^2 = 0.918$), followed by drying air temperature ($\eta_p^2 = 0.808$) and air humidity ($\eta_p^2 = 0.601$) (Table 1). The one-way analysis of variance showed that the induction of PEF technology as a pretreatment led to a significant reduction in TPC in dried apples, regardless of the amount of applied energy (Table S8c). This trend is clearly visible in Fig. 10a and b.

As shown in the literature, PEF can reasonably be used to enhance the extraction of various components from the treated matrix (Mahn, Comett, Segura-Ponce, & Díaz-Álvarez, 2022; Plazzotta et al., 2021; Visockis et al., 2021). The obtained results suggest that the phenomenon of electroporation, by increasing the permeability of the cell membrane, caused the release of phenolic compounds from the cellular structures of the apple tissue, which made them degrade faster and easier in the drying process (Matys, Dadan, et al., 2022; Wiktor et al., 2021). Temperature is one of the factors that can lead to chemical transformations of polyphenols (e.g. epimerization), causing their instability (Deng, Yang, Capanoglu, Cao, & Xiao, 2018). The results of the one-way analysis of variance confirm that the highest TPC was obtained after drying of apples at an air temperature of 70 °C (Table S8b). The lowest and the highest temperatures used (55 and 85 °C) resulted in a long exposure of polyphenols to low temperature and a short exposure of polyphenols to high temperature, respectively (Fig. 3a and b). This could be the reason for the reduced TPC in dried apples. Considering only the effect of air humidity, compared to non-dehumidified air, dehumidified air led to a significant decrease in TPC in dried apples (Table S8a). As proven by the research carried out on a banana, higher air humidity ensured a lower internal temperature of the dried material, which prevented excessive degradation of thermolabile components, such as polyphenols (Sarpong, Yu, Zhou, Amenorfe, et al., 2018).

3.3.6. Antioxidant activity

Figs. 11 and 12 (a, b) show the results of the DPPH and ABTS assays, respectively. The multi-way analysis of variance revealed that air humidity had the highest impact on the antioxidant activity (EC_{50} DPPH) of dried apples ($\eta_p^2 = 0.933$), followed by PEF energy input ($\eta_p^2 = 0.927$) and drying air temperature ($\eta_p^2 = 0.914$). Slightly different tendency was obtained in the case of ABTS assay - the highest impact on the antioxidant activity (EC_{50} ABTS) of dried apples had PEF energy input ($\eta_p^2 = 0.922$), followed by air humidity ($\eta_p^2 = 0.899$) and drying air temperature ($\eta_p^2 = 0.876$) (Table 1). Analyzing the impact of each categorical factor separately (using one-way analysis of variance), the lowest both EC_{50} DPPH and EC_{50} ABTS, and thus the highest antioxidant activity, was achieved for PEF energy input of 0 kJ/kg (untreated apples) (Tables S9c and S10c), air temperature of 70 °C (Tables S9b and S10b), and air humidity equaled 10 g/m³ (Tables S9a and S10a). Many publications demonstrate a negative correlation between total phenolic content and antioxidant activity (expressed as EC_{50} coefficient) (Gülçin, Küfrevioğlu, Oktay, & Büyükkuroğlu, 2004; Gülçin, Küfrevioğlu, Oktay, & Büyükkuroğlu, 2004; Matys, Dadan, et al., 2022; Sultana, Anwar, Ashraf, & Nazamid, 2012; Yildiz and Izli, 2019; Zhou et al., 2016), which is also indicated by the obtained results.

4. Conclusions

This study confirmed that the pulsed electric field can be effectively used to accelerate the drying process of apples with dehumidified and non-dehumidified air. However, increasing the permeability of the cell membrane tends to have both disadvantages and benefits. Along with water molecules, intensive diffusion of other ingredients may occur, which, thanks to their release from cellular structures, are more exposed to thermal and oxidative degradation during drying. Therefore, in order to obtain a high-quality product, it is extremely important to properly select the parameters of both unit operations.

Contrary to the literature data, the dehumidified air did not accelerate the convective drying of apples. This result could have derived from the case hardening, which, in addition to limiting the diffusion of water during drying, reduced the reconstitute properties of the obtained dried materials. Moreover, apples dried with such a drying agent exhibited a higher total color difference (calculated in relation to raw apple), lower total phenolic content, and lower antioxidant activity. This observation can be explained by the intensification of oxidative reactions by lower humidity, and the likely higher internal temperature of

the samples during drying with such agent.

Author contributions

Aleksandra Matys - conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, software, visualization, writing - original draft, writing - review & editing.

Dorota Witrowa-Rajchert - conceptualization, formal analysis, supervision, validation.

Oleksii Parniakov - conceptualization, formal analysis.

Artur Wiktor - conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, validation, writing - review & editing.

Industrial relevance

Dehumidified air has a higher potential in terms of removing water from the material in comparison to non-dehumidified air, which can significantly accelerate the drying process. Application of a pulsed electric field as a pretreatment can modify the properties of the cell membrane and, as a result, affect the diffusivity of water molecules. The combination of these techniques can ensure satisfactory quality of dried products obtained by the convective method, which is generally recognized as the most destructive among the others but is nevertheless widely used in the food industry.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 817683 (acronym FOX).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2023.115455>.

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